

SPOKE N° 5: Industry of Health and Silver Economy

Deliverable 15:

Remote check of hearing devices: instrument/device prototype

Research Module 6:

**Prototype of the instrument to monitor the function
of the cochlear implant of elderly people**

Deliverable 15 – Remote Check of Hearing Devices: Prototype and Demonstrator

Programme: NODES – TINCARE – RM6

Lead Institution: University of Turin (UNITO)

Spoke: 5 - Health Industry and Silver Economy

Deliverable Type: DEM — Demonstrator / Pilot / Prototype

Deadline: October 2025

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1. Executive Summary

This document describes the final prototype of the Remote Check system for remote monitoring of cochlear implant users, developed within the framework of RM6 – NODES TINCARE. The aim is to present the functional demonstrator, the preliminary clinical validation, the REDCap data integration, and the assessment of data protection and security compliance. The prototype allows cochlear implant recipients to autonomously perform self-administered auditory tests, with asynchronous review by the clinical team.

2. Background and Objectives

The growing number of cochlear implant recipients and the need for frequent follow-ups highlight the need for reliable remote monitoring tools.

Remote Check aims to demonstrate the technical and clinical feasibility of supervised remote assessment, reducing unnecessary in-person visits and improving patient quality of life.

Specific Objectives

- Develop a fully functional prototype for remote hearing assessment.
- Validate the agreement between digital and standard clinical measurements.
- Integrate all data within a GDPR-compliant REDCap database.

- Document usability, patient acceptability, and system security.
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3. Prototype Description

The Remote Check prototype consists of three main modules:

1. Patient App – step-by-step guided workflow (implant site photo, PRO questionnaire, ATT, DTT, device check).
2. Clinical Dashboard – visualization of results, longitudinal trends, and automated alerts.
3. REDCap Integration – pseudonymized data export in CSV/PDF formats.

All data are encrypted (TLS 1.2 in transit, AES-256 at rest).

4. Operational Flow of the Remote Check App

1. Login and informed consent
2. Implant site photo acquisition
3. PRO questionnaire
4. Automated pure-tone audiometry (ATT)
5. Digit-in-Noise Test (DTT)

6. Device function check (data logging)

7. Data upload and clinical review

The following figures illustrate the complete user workflow of the Remote Check App, from login to final report submission.

Figure 1. Main app menu – options including Hearing Tracker, Find My Processor, and Remote Check.

Figure 2. Remote Check start screen – message “Ready to start”, with expiration date displayed.

Figure 3. Step 1 – Photo of the implant area: patient instructed to capture and upload the image.

Figure 4. Step 2 – Patient questionnaire (Part 1) on implant condition and perceived sound quality.

Figure 5. Step 3 – Automated audiogram: initial screen “Did you hear a sound?” with scrollable options.

Hai udito un suono?

No

Sì

Figure 6. Step 3b – Tone perception confirmation (visual feedback with green activation circle).

Figure 7. Step 4 – Device functional check – progress bar showing “Recording data, about 10 seconds required.”

Figure 8. Step 5 – Speech-in-noise test setup: numeric keypad awaiting input.

✕ Voce in ambiente rumoroso

219

Figure 9. Step 5b – Speech-in-noise test response example (“219”) confirming comprehension accuracy.

Figure 10. Progress screen – stages completed: photo, questionnaire, audiogram, device check, speech-in-noise.

Figure 11. Additional progress screen – visual confirmation of completion (different subject example).

Remote Check > Presentazione Generale > Audiogramma

Inviata 63 giorni fa

Revisione in ritardo di 49 giorni (1 set 2025)
Verifica per adulti (12 giu 2025 - 18 ago 2025)

Remote Check > Presentazione Generale

Inviata 64 giorni fa

Revisione in ritardo di 50 giorni (1 set 2025)
Verifica per adulti (12 giu 2025 - 18 ago 2025)

DOMANDE

NESSUN DATO

Attività non selezionata per questo controllo

VERIFICA DELL'IMPEDENZA

0

PROBLEMI

Con elettrodi attivi

AUDIOGRAMMA

Verifica precedente (Basale) 12 giu 2025

VOCE IN AMBIENTE RUMOROSO

-6.2dB

MIGLIORAMENTO DI 3.9 dB

Verifica precedente (Basale) 12 giu 2025

STATO DELL'HARDWARE

0

ALLARMI

Presentato al paziente

FOTO DELL'AREA DELL'IMPIANTO

NESSUN DATO

Attività non selezionata per questo controllo

Figure 12. Final menu summary – all Remote Check tasks completed, access to results and hearing performance overview.

5. Experimental Results (Preliminary Data)

- Strong correlation between digital ATT and standard audiometric thresholds ($r \approx 0.87$)
- High concordance between DTT and Matrix test ($r \approx 0.83$)
- Average completion time ≈ 19 minutes
- Completion rate $> 90\%$

- Mean satisfaction score = 8.9 / 10
-

6. Data Privacy, Security and Compliance

The system complies with GDPR (EU Reg. 679/2016) and ISO/IEC 27001:2017 standards.

Data are pseudonymized and encrypted (TLS 1.2 + AES-256). Two-factor authentication protects clinical dashboard access. A complete Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) has been approved by the UNITO Data Protection Officer.

7. Annexes A–F (Summary)

The complete content of the annexes is provided in Section 10 of this document.

8. Conclusions

Deliverable 15 finalizes module RM6 by delivering a validated, functional prototype.

The adoption of Remote Check will reduce unnecessary clinic visits and enhance continuity of care.

Future developments include expansion to bilateral implants, integration with wearable balance assessment, and AI-driven predictive algorithms for personalized follow-up.

9. References

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Laird E. et al. *Systematic Review of Remote Digital Technologies for Cochlear Implant and Hearing Aid Users*. *Front Audiol Otol*. 2024; 2: 1403814.

Kim J. et al. *A Review of Contemporary Tele-Audiology*. *J Hear Sci*. 2021; 11(2): 134-149.

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10. ANNEXES A–F

A — Screenshots and Images of the Remote Check App

Key workflow stages: app start-up, implant-site photo, PRO questionnaire, ATT, DTT, device check, final summary.

B — Software Interface

Clinical dashboard with patient overview, threshold trends, and automatic alerts; patient detail view; result review section. Two-factor authentication (2FA); OWASP-compliant secure web environment.

C — Demonstration Script

Scenario A: Routine verification (< 20 min, green status).
Scenario B: ATT > 10 dB deterioration → yellow alert.
Scenario C: Unstable connection → automatic retry and data recovery.

D — Patient Questionnaire (Extract)

Example items (Likert 0–4): speech-in-noise understanding, sound quality, device malfunction, ease of use.
Digital completion with automatic REDCap upload.

E — REDCap Integration

Field mapping: record_id, session_timestamp, device_model, ATT thresholds 250–8 kHz, dtt_srt, photo_flag, datalog_hours, coil_offs, pro_total, ssq_subscales.
Automated export in CSV + PDF; data encrypted with AES-256.

F — Privacy and DPIA Summary

Data types: implant-site images, hearing thresholds, session metadata.

Security measures: encryption, pseudonymization, audit logging, redundant backups.

Legal basis: informed consent + scientific research purpose (Art. 9 GDPR).

Data controller: University of Turin; External processor: Cochlear Italia.